

Clash of Competitions: A Study on Coaching Classes of Kota

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Abstract:

The news of suicide by coaching student has become a common phenomenon in these days. Sometimes over ambitions on the part of parents, circumstances, in ability on the part of students, conflict between dream of students and parents expectation produces conflict. The American newspaper, The Washington Post published that more than 70 students have committed suicide in the last five years in Kota city of Rajasthan, India. It is quite evident in the report of the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) that the rate of these suicides is much higher than the national average of 10.6 suicides per one hundred thousand (100,000) people in 2014. According to this report the suicides are committed by hanging self, ablaze self and by jumping from the heights. (Bray and Lykins, 2012) found also that the private supplementary tutoring is widely known as shadow education, since it mimics the mainstream. This research paper is not committed to resolve the suicidal tendency but only focusing on the clash of competitions where conflict arouses to tendencies for suicidal commitment among students.

Key words: Competitions, Coaching, Suicide, Kota, NCRB.

Coaching classes today have become an essential part of a child's education in India. The trend, which was once considered vexing by parents, is now utterly unavoidable. According to the Asian Development Bank Report entitled *Shadow Education: Private Supplementary Tutoring and Its Implications for Policy Makers in Asia*, the coaching sector is estimated to be growing at over 15 per cent each year. As per the 2012 report by the Asian Development Bank (ADB), about 83 per cent of India's high school children attend coaching classes. The daily newspaper 'Business Standard' says seeing the potential of the coaching business in the Indian market; foreigners too are investing heavily in this arena. In 2011, South Korean coaching giant *Etoos* invested Rs 30 Crores to set up its centres in Kota, focusing on video lecturing and e-learning.

In the past two decades Kota city has emerged as a popular coaching destination for preparation of competitive exams and education become the main economic base. It's an education hub for all Indians and neighboring countries because of its world class coaching's and studies. It is estimated that every year two hundred thousand students are coming here to get coaching of IIT- JEE (Indian Institute of Technology- Joint Entrance Examination), PMT (Pre-Medical Test), CPMT (Central Pre-Medical Test), AIEEE (All India Engineering Entrance Examination) etc. with the hope that after getting coaching they will be selected in their competitive exams. So to fulfill their dreams for becoming doctor and engineer young brains are leaving their families, relatives and childhood friends at their home town (Prajapati & Singh, 2015). Whereas, Narayana Murthy, the founder of Infosys, criticised coachings during his speech to former IITians at 'Pan IIT' summit on October 3, 2011 at New York that "*the quality of students entering Indian Institutes of Technology (IITs) has deteriorated over the years due to the coaching classes that prepare engineering aspirants.*"

THE TOP PLAYERS IN KOTA

	YEAR FOUNDED	NUMBER OF STUDENTS	CENTRES	PE/VC FUNDING/ BACKING
BANSAL CLASSES	1983	17,000	Kota	—
RESONANCE EDUVENTURES	2001	21,000	Across multiple cities—all company owned	Rs 100 crore from CLSA, Rs 60 crore from Milestone Religare
CAREER POINT	1993	20,000	Across multiple cities, distance learning	Franklin Templeton PE invested Rs 50 crore in 2009, and up to \$10 million by Nadathur Group, owned by NS Raghavan of Infosys
VIBRANT ACADEMY	2009	9,200	Kota	—
ALLEN CAREER INSTITUTE	1988	30,000	Kota	—

Figure 1 (Top Coaching Players in Kota)
 (Source: <http://www.forbesindia.com/printcontent/33050>)

The foundation of the coaching industry at Kota, Rajasthan was laid down in early 1980s by V. K. Bansal, an engineer at a J. K. Synthetics factory who began his teaching career by taking math tuitions for local students. Slowly, his students started clearing the IIT exams. In 1986, Kota came in the IIT limelight when local boy Sanjeev Arora topped the entrance exam. Bansal says that 13 of his students cracked the entrance test in 1990. In the mid-1990s, after the closure of the J. K. Synthetics factory, several engineers joined Bansal Classes. Many of them later started their own institutes.

The comparative success rate of coaching institutes (Based on availability on their respective website)

Figure (2) Students selected from Major Coaching’s of Kota in 2017

Need of the study

It is seen that at the time of examination students become monkey mind or imbalanced. Therefore, students or children are sent to coaching classes for their study. Leaving too little, this is where the tension begins to arise in the students. Today a range of coaching classes is available in every big city of India. In the Kota city of Rajasthan, there is a vast range of coaching institutions for IIT, Engineering, Medical and Non-Medical courses; where about the student of every corner of India is coming for coaching for most of IIT, Engineering and Medical courses. Cook (2017) has warned in his note which was published in *Pittsburgh Post-Gazette*, that the stress of coaching and the pressure to win sometimes can be a question of life or death. According to *The Huffington Post*, till April 2017, Fifty seven (57) coaching students have finished their life with their own hands. It can be commonly experienced that the students have a variety of stresses about various competitive examinations, related to the environment, feeling, choice, and often their fears of being selected into IIT, Engineering and Medical courses.

The issue is serious and should be taken into account with utmost care and sensitivity. This small study is intended to look into the problem and how the problem may be resolved.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are as follows-

1. To study the satisfaction level of students who are pursuing coaching for IIT, Engineering and Medical courses in Kota city of Rajasthan.
2. To study the perception of teachers of coaching institution in regard of different dimensions of the students study and life skill.

3. To study the accommodative facilities which are being provided to the coaching students in hostels of Kota city in Rajasthan.
4. To identify the dark area of coaching institute with respect to students overall expectation and performance.
5. To provide suggestions to overcome problems of hostel life and stress of coaching students.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

A mixed method sequential explanatory study was undertaken using questionnaires for (1) Students (2) Teachers and (3) Hostel owner's satisfaction. In the first quantitative phase, questionnaires were administered to students of various coaching institutes and hostel owners of Kota. 400 questionnaires were distributed for collecting data but only 300 questionnaires were properly filled and returned back by the students who were pursuing coaching for IIT, Engineering and Medical courses in year 2017. The same process was opted for collecting the data from teachers / counselors / instructors of coaching institutes. 150 questionnaires were distributed to teachers of coaching institutes of Kota where 100 questionnaires were completely filled and returned back by the teachers / counselors / instructors of coaching institutes. For seeking the opinion of hostel owners 25 questionnaire was distributed out of which 20 questionnaires was returned back the hostel owners.

On the basis of the data collected from the students, teachers and hostel owner's further study was undertaken.

Research design

Mixed method research is gaining increasing acceptance in social science fields such as sociology, nursing, health and education (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2007). For this study

sequential explanatory research design of mixed method is used. It involves a two-phase study in which the research moves from quantitative phase to qualitative phase sequentially.

Sample and sampling technique:

Purposive sampling

In this research *purposive and random sampling technique* was used where samples of coaching students and hostel owners were selected randomly. The selected sample size for the study was 400 students and 150 teachers / counselors / instructors and 25 hostel owners.

Limitations

The study was limited to the students who were pursuing coaching only for IIT, Engineering and Medical courses in Kota. The results are dependent on methodological limitations and limitations of the tools.

Procedure of data collection

The data for sample were collected from 400 coaching students and 150 teachers and 25 hostel owners using three separate questionnaires by performing a survey. 300 coaching students, 100 teachers and 20 hostel owners returned back the filled questionnaire.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A study was conducted involving 400 students attending different coaching institutes selected on the criteria that the student is attending some coaching class. The responses of 300 students were collected and tabulated on a fixed response questionnaire containing Eight (8) major dimensions as *Health & Sports, Yoga & Meditation, Study Habits, Environmental*

Conditions, Infrastructural Facilities, Food Habits, Self-Identification and, Tension & Stress. The responses on these dimensions are given below-

Figure (3) Student Satisfaction Survey

The above data, which are obtained dimension wise, provide ideas as we see in the above Figure (3) -

Health & Sports:

59.13% of students reported that they are actively aware about their health and the activities like daily running, playing some physical games, practice at gymnasium etc. which help to improve the health. Other 40.87% students were known about the benefits from games but due to busy time schedule, they were not free to play.

Yoga & Meditation:

In this study we found that 25% students were engaged in practicing Yoga and Meditation & *Surya Namaskara* daily or on free time but 75% students were spending their free time by playing games, seeing television, listening to songs, walking, etc.

Study Habits:

Only 35.33% students' study habits were not in managed form while 64.67% arranged their time for systematic study in coaching as well as in hostel.

Environmental Conditions:

66.50% students were found satisfied with the environmental conditions of hostel like the place where hostel was established, ventilation, air flow system and accordance to seasons like winter, summer and rainy season.

Infrastructure Facilities:

21% students complained about room conditions, height of roof, wardrobe, toilets, congestion and problem of suffocation while 79% were satisfied with the infrastructural facilities of hostels.

Food Quality:

Only 78% students were dissatisfied with the food quality of the food which was given in hostels but a galore of students (22%) were enjoying with food.

Self-Identification:

A few students near about 47% were aware for self entity while about 53% were ignorance about to know the self in terms of personality, attitude and capabilities.

Tension & Stress:

62% students were found in tension and stress while 38% were free from it. Reason of tension and stress was due to tough selection procedure, family pressure, no friend circle, no game, no music and no leisure activity to release stress and tension.

Findings on the basis of responses of students:

1. Average number of students is satisfied with their studies, however satisfactions with coaching is lesser.
2. Almost half of the students are hopeful for their success.
3. Most of the students reported about having no time for game and sports.

4. Most of the students reported a high pressure from their parents for success.
5. Hostel facilities as reported are satisfactory only.
6. Most of the students reported having no time to watch movies.
7. A major concern is that the most of students reported that they are attending coaching as per their parents' wishes.
8. Most of the students are of the opinion that sports may release the pressure and stress.
9. *Surya Namskara* and other activities are needed to be encouraged.

Teacher/Counsellor/Instructor Survey

For the present study data was collected from 150 teacher/counselor/instructors who are teaching in coaching institutions of Kota city. Only 100 questionnaires were returned back by them. The questionnaire consists of Eight (8) dimensions as Health & Sports, Yoga & Meditation, Study Habits, Environmental Conditions, Infrastructural Facilities, Self-Confidence and, Tension & Stress.

Figure (4) Teacher/Counsellor/Instructor Opinion Survey

The above data, which are obtained dimension wise, are the basis of the ideas mentioned in the above Figure (4). 49% teachers/counselor/instructors believe that there is a little facility to maintain health and for sports activities because of lack of time and formality for norms by coaching owners. While

51% refused for availability of, game and health kit in coaching institution.

39% said yes for practicing yoga and meditation in coaching classes but only for 30 minutes before starting the classes. Other 61% showed incapability of practicing Yoga owing to other problems like little space, time schedule, tough instructions by the institution owners etc.

Most of teachers 37% appreciate the timing schedule, management, study material, etc. for better study habits of the students but 63% said it very busy and fatiguing schedule.

88% teachers said that there are good environmental conditions and 92% teachers showed satisfaction towards infrastructural conditions like building, hostel, mess, lighting, ventilation, air flow, space in classrooms, etc. A less amount of teacher 12% for environmental conditions and 8% for infrastructural facilities were dissatisfied in regard of these facilities.

Only 44% teachers/counselor/instructors were satisfied with the self-confidence of the students whereas 56% were worried for the lack of self-confidence of the coaching students. 81% teachers/counselor/instructors says that they identify the stress among students but they are not well equipped to counter the stress problems in terms of training and specialty, while 19% replied that they come across the thousands of students daily so they are not able to identify the problems of students.

Hostels and Hostel Facilities (Based upon the response of hostel owners)

There are an estimated more than 800 private hostels in Indra Vihar, Talwandi, Vigyan Nagar and Rajeev Gandhi Nagar localities alone. Overall, nearly 70 per cent of Kota's economy depends on these businesses. In recent years, however, growing competition among coaching centres has led to simpler entrance

tests. Most institutes admit almost all students who apply as they do not want to lose revenue (Malhotra, 2013).

In order to assess the quality of hostel facilities in context of recreation, leisure and medical facilities at different hostels available nearby coaching institutes was conducted using a fixed response questionnaire. 25 small and big hostels were selected randomly having at least the capacity of accommodating 30 students. But only 20 hostel owner responded for the research. The result on seven (7) dimensions is as below-

Figure (5) Hostel Owner Satisfaction Survey

As the chart indicates, 70% of hostels arranged high level infrastructural facilities like space in room, ventilation, toilets, sleeping beds, study tables, lighting, easy approachable to coaching classes etc. while 30% hostels were out of approach of coaching institutions.

Majority of 65% hostels have only televisions and cable connections in canteens to entertainment only at the time of breakfast, lunch and dinner. In the other hand 35% hostel owner believe that television with set top box or dish cable creates hurdles in the study of the students. No other recreational facilities were found there in most of hostels.

Almost no hostel has any sports facility, which was the major finding of this survey research. Although one hostel owner said that he is having the facility of games and sports

but during the observation of the available facility that was found almost useless.

45% hostel owners were found to behave like guardian of the students but 55% were not interested to interfere in life of students.

A majority about 75% of hostel owner refused to feel any type of external conflict in the students. But they did not say anything on internal conflict.

According to the 75% hostel owners says that most of students feels loneliness at the time of any occasion such as on examination or some festivals etc. while 25% hostel owner replied that they do not bother about the students.

90% hostel owners were not aware about the safety of the students whereas 10% were aware about the safety of the students by following safety precautions like having fire safety cylinder, gatekeeper etc.

Major Findings on the basis of responses of hostel owners

1. Hostels have almost no facility of games and sports.
2. Students who feel alone in hostels.
3. Most of the hostel owners think that students are under great pressure.
4. Hostel owners are not connected to their students. They are actually involved in only money making.
5. Hostels have no medical facility available to them.

The Dark side / Grey area of the story

Headlines "*Inside Kota's coaching factories: Pressure, anxiety prey on students*" of May, 15, 2016 of newspaper *Hindustan Times* exposed the dark side of coaching institutions. The mushrooming coaching industry of Kota has a dark side as well.

- 1. Lack of Sports Activity:** This study reveals clearly that Kota coaching industry is lacking in terms of sports facility in coaching centers as well as in the hostels. **The major concern of government and coaching centers should be the encouragement of sports activity.** This study reveals that games and sports facility will surely work in the direction of releasing the pressure and stress which will surely work in the direction of lessening the suicides.
- 2. Lack of Guidance and Psychological Counseling Services:** The counseling services are almost unavailable in the coaching centres. The counseling services should be enhanced to save the students from the depression and stress. This research reflects that available counselors are not well equipped in taking up the serious issue of suicide among the students. The qualified and properly trained psychological counselors should be appointed by the coaching centres for providing better counseling services.
- 3. Divisions of Students in categories have and haven't:** Various scholars has expressed their worries on growing private tutoring practices indicating the disparity between students who have some specific facilities and who have not. For example, Kota has many hostels providing AC Rooms@15000-20000 INR per month. Clearly it is not easy for parents of Middle income group to afford this. As a result many students hire shared room and depend upon Mess for their food. It increases the disparity between so called rich and poor students which causes conflict and an inferiority complex among poor students. Perhaps *Amartya Sen* is right when he mentions that that private tutoring divides the student population into haves and have-nots; it makes teachers less responsible and it diminishes their central role in education; it makes improvements

in schooling arrangements more difficult since the more influential and better placed families have less at stake in the quality of what is done in the schools.

4. **A Negative Socio-Educational Trend of Dummy Schools:** Owing to growing culture of coaching in Kota, Dummy School Culture has been grown up which is a serious issue. As these coaching institutes conducts preparatory classes since class 6th during day time, it is difficult for students to attend classes at affiliated schools from where they will get the degree. Coaching Institutes come with a solution of this by providing enrolment option in a dummy school where student need not attend regular classes. On a nominal payment at those affiliated schools, a student gets enrolment, gets attendance without attending the school appears in the board examination and gets degree of 10th and 12th classes.
5. **Suicides among students:** Kota witness several cases of suicide every year. As Malhotra (2013) observed *“The town witnesses at least a dozen suicides a year by engineering aspirants. Psychiatrist C.S. Sushil, a professor at Kota Medical College, says the problem of depression is growing among students. He says the town has 11 psychiatrists, who attend at least five children daily on average. In most cases, these students were toppers in their schools, villages and states. But when they come here, amidst a line of toppers from across India, their rank falls. “At the back of a student’s mind is the fear of being a failure and all the money that his family has spent on him,” says Sushil. He adds that, since children come here at a young age, they suffer from separation anxiety disorder due to staying away from home for a prolonged period. “Such cases have shot up in the past seven-eight year.*

6. Juvenile Delinquency: Apart from Suicides, increased crime rate is common in Kota which is frequent and committed usually by Juvenile Delinquents. Students coming from rural background comewith a dream of being reach by becoming a reputed Doctor or Engineer. Sometime due to any reason they are not able to cope up but high aspirations of their parents does not allow them to go back to their home. In such a case to earn money in a shortcut way they choose the illegal way like theft, robbery, kidnapping etc. As Prajapati & Singh observed that *“Kota in Rajasthan is a place where lacs of students are coming to take coaching for their competitive exams but apart from studies they are indulging in several crime, delinquent behaviour and acts. In this paper researcher tries to find out the causes and effect on society of Juvenile delinquency. Self-constructed questionnaire and checklist were used to collect data. In-depth interviews were conducted with psychologists, doctors, police officers and care takers of rehabilitation centres and borstal. 100-100 psychologists, police officers, parents, borstal and hostel care takers were selected as sample through purposive sampling method. Mostly delinquents are associated with the stealing, forged signatures, damaging property of schools and their coaching, bullying and mockery, torturing, using abusing language, exhibitionism, homo sexuality, hetero sexuality, making sexual suggestions, masturbation, obscene drawing and pictures, regardless of gender, robbery, smuggling, drug trafficking, truancy etc. but very less students are involved in committing suicide, prostitution, murder and rape. The study revealed the reasons behind this juvenile delinquency are family influences, films and television, school factors, peer group and geographic influences and scholastic attainment, body build and disabilities, physiological characteristics,*

personality characteristics, and genetic factors. As a result it was found that parents' observation and supervision must require controlling and yoga, meditation, motivational seminar and conferences, individual and group counselling are important sources to stop diverting children in criminal acts and measures for prevention of juvenile delinquency”.

Suggestions to overcome problems of hostel life and stress

A great atmosphere can shape or distort a hostel life. Having daily activities obviously helps improve hostel atmosphere and of course, lots of hostels are doing this right! But smaller places or newly-opened ones might lack the resources, either human or financial, necessary to establish a weekly schedule of on-site activities. Here are some ways that might help improve hostel atmosphere.

1. **Give priority to your studies:** This is difficult especially in India where we enter the college/coaching after lots of hard work and expect enjoyment there. We have often heard from our parents “First get into a college then enjoy yourself and do whatever you want to do”.
2. **Arrangement for sports and game facility:** This study reveals clearly that Kota coaching industry is lacking in terms of sports facility in coaching centers as well as in the hostels. The major concern of government and coaching centers should be the encouragement of sports activity.
3. **Arrangement of Guidance and Psychological Counseling Services:** The counseling services are almost unavailable in the coaching centres. The counseling services should be enhanced to save the students from the

depression and stress. The qualified psychological counselors should be appointed by the coaching centres for better counseling services.

4. **Build meaningful friendships:** To make a better and happy environment every person wants of friends. So it is necessary to make a peer group to overcome loneliness.
5. **Say no to drugs:** Never take drugs to release the mental pressure. These are not for a healthy body. These are the reason of memory losses.
6. **Join a society:** To overcome on burden and stress of study join a society it may be sports, music, dance and literary club.
7. **Change up your routine:** If you've always been a competitive runner, take a look at other less competitive options that may help with stress reduction, such as Pilates or yoga classes. As an added bonus, these kinder, gentler workouts may enhance your running while also decreasing your stress. Believe it that Hostel is the place of cure for homesickness. Say your problems with the hostel owner and your room mate.
8. **Identify your interests:** Think about what you want to do next in your life. Help yourself to decide aim of your life and remember it. Every time feels that there are many people that love you and they are dreaming for you.
9. **Love yourself:** Some time it is necessary to be selfish. There will be a lot of people backbiting about you, don't cares about them, love yourself.
10. **Exercise and stress relief:** Exercise increases your overall health and your sense of well-being, which puts more pep in your step every day. But exercise also has some direct stress-busting benefits.

- a. **It pumps up your endorphins:** Physical activity helps bump up the production of your brain's feel-good neurotransmitters, called endorphins. Although this function is often referred to as a runner's high, a rousing game of tennis or a nature hike also can contribute to this same feeling.
- b. **It's meditation in motion:** After a fast-paced game of racquetball or several laps in the pool, you'll often find that you've forgotten the day's irritations and concentrated only on your body's movements. As you begin to regularly shed your daily tensions through movement and physical activity, you may find that this focus on a single task, and the resulting energy and optimism, can help you remain calm and clear in everything you do.
- c. **It improves your mood:** Regular exercise can increase self-confidence, it can relax you, and it can lower the symptoms associated with mild depression and anxiety. Exercise can also improve your sleep, which is often disrupted by stress, depression and anxiety. All of these exercise benefits can ease your stress levels and give you a sense of command over your body and your life.

CONCLUSION

The preliminary study on student's satisfaction indicated an average level of satisfaction of students at different coaching institutes of Kota. A relatively higher number of students

reported that they are fulfilling their parent's wish which is a major concern. Students feel very high pressure from parents, peers and coaching and thus study hours are longer for them and less likely to get indulged in game and sports and recreational activities. Most of the coachings do not have provision of any type of co-curricular activities or no provision of any type of psychological counselling to overcome the stress. Sometimes coaching's focus on only students of their top batches to be taught by top teachers to grow their business, remaining other students are not taken care of properly. Due to the growing coaching industry a trend of dummy schools has been developed, juvenile delinquency has also been increased and as disparity between who have and who don't have has been increasing. High pressure to succeed has made students a study machine only increasing suicide rates and such tendency among students. Hostel facilities are average depending upon the payment capacity of individual students. Accommodation ranges from well-furnished room with AC and mess to separate room without facility with a monthly rental of 20000 INR to 4000 INR respectively.

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